

Benchmarking of Artificial Intelligence and Radiologists for Lung Cancer Screening in CT: The LUNA25 Challenge: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Benchmarking of Artificial Intelligence and Radiologists for Lung Cancer Screening in CT: The LUNA25 Challenge

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

LUNA25

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, with 2.5 million people diagnosed and 1.8 million deaths occurring annually worldwide (Bray et al., 2024). The National Lung Cancer Screening Trial (NLST) and the Dutch-Belgian lung cancer screening trial (NELSON) provided evidence that the lung cancer mortality can be reduced by repeated screening of high-risk individuals with low-dose chest CT (de Koning et al., 2020; Aberle et al., 2011). Lung cancer screening could therefore play an important role in reducing lung cancer mortality. However, implementation of lung cancer screening will further increase the already high workload on radiologists.

This imminent implementation of lung cancer screening and growing workload for radiologists demonstrates the need for safe and validated artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, which have already shown human level performance for lung nodule malignancy risk estimation (Venkadesh et al., 2021). However, it remains challenging to adequately validate and benchmark the increasing amount of AI algorithms being developed. For this, Grand challenges, which are international public competitions, offer the means to compare and validate AI algorithms. LUNA16 (Setio et al., 2017) and the Kaggle 2017 Data Science Bowl are examples of such competitions to train and validate AI algorithms. However, since then the field of AI has progressed a lot, the interest of radiologists has increased and better datasets have been collected, which opens the door for a more reliable comparison of AI algorithms and radiologists in lung cancer screening.

The LUNA25 challenge is new grand challenge designed to evaluate the performance of AI algorithms and radiologists in lung nodule malignancy risk estimation in screening CT. LUNA25 aims to establish: 1) state-of-the-art AI performance for lung nodule malignancy risk estimation, 2) performance of radiologists at lung

nodule malignancy risk estimation through a large scale international reader study, 3) a comparison between performance of AI algorithms and radiologists with varying levels of experience. This study hypothesizes that state-of-the-art AI performs non-inferior to the average radiologist in estimating lung nodule malignancy risk on screening CT scans. However, this study does not address AI workflow integration or radiologist-AI interaction.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Lung cancer, artificial intelligence, computed tomography, screening, diagnosis

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The LUNA25 challenge aims to bring AI research one step closer to the clinical practice of lung nodule analysis. Previous challenges like LUNA16 and the Kaggle 2017 Data Science Bowl focused on lung nodule detection and case-based lung cancer prediction on CT. However, with LUNA25, we will not focus on nodule detection but on malignancy risk classification.

For this, we are releasing, to our knowledge, the largest dataset of well-annotated lung nodules and corresponding malignancy labels. This provides researchers the opportunity to develop and evaluate their AI models for lung nodule malignancy risk estimation on CT.

Additionally, LUNA25 aims to establish a, currently unavailable, standardized benchmark that enables AI developers to test and evaluate their models on a held-out external dataset for lung nodule malignancy risk estimation. In parallel, LUNA25 will conduct a reader study that allows to compare the developed AI models with a panel of radiologists.

In conclusion, the LUNA25 challenge will determine the leading AI model and method for lung cancer classification at screening CTs and offers insights into how AI compares to human readers.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Classification

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

Not applicable.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect a number of 20-30 participating teams based on the number of previous challenges like LUNA16, PI-CAI and the experience of the grand-challenge support team.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, ultimately the goal of this challenge is to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Grand-Challenge platform (similar to rse-GC-workshop)

TASK 1: Lung Nodule Risk Estimation in low-dose computed tomography (CT)

SUMMARY

Abstract

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Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, with 2.5 million people diagnosed and 1.8 million deaths occurring annually worldwide (Bray et al., 2024). The National Lung Cancer Screening Trial (NLST) and the Dutch-Belgian lung cancer screening trial (NELSON) provided evidence that the lung cancer mortality can be reduced by repeated screening of high-risk individuals with low-dose chest CT (de Koning et al., 2020; Aberle et al., 2011). Lung cancer screening could therefore play an important role in reducing lung cancer mortality. However, implementation of lung cancer screening will further increase the already high workload on radiologists.

This imminent implementation of lung cancer screening and growing workload for radiologists demonstrates the need for safe and validated artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, which have already shown human level performance for lung nodule malignancy risk estimation (Venkadesh et al., 2021). However, it remains challenging to adequately validate and benchmark the increasing amount of AI algorithms being developed. For this, Grand challenges, which are international public competitions, offer the means to compare and validate AI algorithms. LUNA16 (Setio et al., 2017) and the Kaggle 2017 Data Science Bowl are examples of such competitions to train and validate AI algorithms. However, since then the field of AI has progressed a lot, the interest of radiologists has increased and better datasets have been collected, which opens the door for a more reliable comparison of AI algorithms and radiologists in lung cancer screening.

The LUNA25 challenge is new grand challenge designed to evaluate the performance of AI algorithms and radiologists in lung nodule malignancy risk estimation in screening CT. LUNA25 aims to establish: 1) state-of-the-art AI performance for lung nodule malignancy risk estimation, 2) performance of radiologists at lung nodule malignancy risk estimation through a large scale international reader study, 3) a comparison between performance of AI algorithms and radiologists with varying levels of experience. This study hypothesizes that state-of-the-art AI performs non-inferior to the average radiologist in estimating lung nodule malignancy risk on screening CT scans. However, this study does not address AI workflow integration or radiologist-AI interaction.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

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ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Dré Peeters, Bogdan Obreja, Noa Antonissen, Colin Jacobs.

All members are part of the Department of Medical imaging, Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Dré Peeters: dre.peeters@radboudumc.nl; Bogdan Obreja: bogdan.obreja@radboudumc.nl; Noa Antonissen: noa.antonissen@radboudumc.nl; Colin Jacobs: colin.jacobs@radboudumc.nl

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event as open call challenge

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

This challenge is not associated with any conference.

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

<https://grand-challenge.org/> will be used as platform to run the challenge. They have also already accepted our challenge on their platform.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://luna25.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed, but such data must be publicly available under a permissive open-source license three months prior to the submission deadline, and its source must be clearly stated.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Teams responsible for developing a top 5 performing AI algorithm will receive cash prizes.

1st: €1000

2nd: €500

3rd: €250

4th: €150

5th: €100

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 5 performing submissions and their respective performance will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

- Up to 3 members from each team, that is responsible for one of the top-performing AI algorithms, will be invited to join the LUNA25 challenge paper, as a consortium author

- Participants of the LUNA25 challenge, as well as non-participating researchers using the LUNA25 public training dataset, can publish their own results separately at any time. They do not have to adhere to any embargo period.

While doing so, they are requested to cite this document (BIAS preregistration form for the LUNA25 challenge), which will be published on Zenodo with a corresponding DOI. Once a study protocol and/or a challenge paper has been published, they are requested to refer to those publications instead.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission (type 2) on Grand Challenge. Instructions for submission can be found at:

<https://grand-challenge.org/documentation/algorithms/>.

For additional information see the next answer (Pre-evaluation).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

1. Open Development Phase:

Anyone can participate in this phase of the challenge. Interested teams can create an account on grand-challenge.org, and register for the LUNA25 challenge at luna25.grand-challenge.org. Afterwards, they will be provided access to download the public training dataset, and in turn, they can start developing and training AI algorithms using their private or public compute resources. Participating teams can also use additional data to train their algorithms, but such data must be publicly available under a permissive open-source license three months prior to the submission deadline, and its source must be clearly stated. Teams can upload and submit their trained algorithms (in Docker containers) for evaluation a maximum of 15 times throughout the challenge. During evaluation, the algorithms are executed on the grand-challenge.org platform, their performance is evaluated on the hidden tuning cohort, and team rankings are updated accordingly on a live, public leaderboard. Facilitating validation in such a manner ensures that any image used for evaluation remains truly unseen, and that AI predictions cannot be tampered with. This allows for bias-free performance estimation.

2. Closed Testing Phase:

After the Development Phase is closed, each registered team can choose to submit a single AI algorithm (presumably their top-performing algorithm) for evaluation on the hidden testing cohort. Based on their performance on this cohort, all new rankings will be drawn and the top 5 algorithms of the LUNA25 challenge will be determined and announced. To qualify as one of the top teams, participants must also submit a short paper on their methodology (2-3 pages) and a public/private URL to their source code on GitHub to ensure fairness, traceability and reproducibility of all proposed solutions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- February 15th: Release of the public training dataset
 - March 1st: Accepting AI algorithms for the Open Development Phase
 - July 1st: Closing the submission for the Open Development Phase
 - July 1st: Accepting AI algorithms for the Closed Testing Phase
 - August 1st: Closing the submission for the Closed Testing Phase
 - September 23rd-27th: Public announcement of the Closed Testing Phase Leaderboard and the LUNA25 Challenge at MICCAI2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference

to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethical approval for the training set was granted with the NLST trial receiving institutional review board approval at all 33 centers participating in the trial. In addition, informed consent was provided by all participants involved in the trial. Access to this dataset was granted through the National Cancer Institute's Cancer Data Access System (CDAS) under project number NLST-74, NLST-111, NLST-164 and NLST-267.

Ethical approvals were obtained from the Ethics Committee of Copenhagen County (DLCST), the institutional review board of Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale Tumori di Milano (MILD), and the Dutch Minister of Health with support from the Dutch Health Council (NELSON), along with authorization from the Ethical Boards of participating centres.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

The LUNA25 training dataset consists of two separate datasets. One dataset contains the imaging data, which will be licensed under a CC-BY 4.0 license. The second dataset contains the annotation data, which will be licensed under a CC-BY-NC 4.0 license. This means that the nodule annotation data can be downloaded and shared for non-commercial purposes, provided that proper credit is given to the challenge. However, the annotation dataset cannot be used for commercial purposes.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The source code for evaluation of the participating AI algorithms will be made publicly available on Github. The link will be available at the start of the challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The source code for training both a baseline 2D ResNet18 model and a 3D-inflated Inception-v1 model is available, packaged in its own Docker container for submission to LUNA25. Participating teams can access them through a Github link which will be made available at the start of the challenge.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Colin Jacobs receives research grants and royalties to host institution from MeVis Medical Solutions, Bremen, Germany; payment for lectures from Canon Medical Systems and Johnson & Johnson. Colin Jacobs is a collaborator in a public-private research project where Radboudumc collaborates with Philips Medical Systems (Best, the Netherlands), and a public-private research project where Radboudumc collaborates with Siemens Healthineers (Erlangen, Germany).

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Research, Screening, Risk Stratification

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The challenge and target cohorts for LUNA25 are very similar as they both represent the same patient populations: individuals eligible for lung cancer screening. These populations include both men and women who are at high risk of developing lung cancer. Inclusion criteria for lung cancer screening include factors such as age, history of heavy smoking (measured in pack-years), and whether the individuals are current smokers or have quit smoking within the last 10-15 years, depending on the screening trial. Nonetheless, deviations in the challenge cohorts with respect to the target cohort do exist, due to the following factors:

- Cases from the training dataset and hidden test set were excluded for the following reasons: poor scan quality, artifacts, or incomplete imaging.
- Absence of patient scans in the training datasets, and the hidden test set, acquired using scanners besides GE Healthcare, Siemens, Toshiba, and Philips.
- For the reader study a cancer enriched cohort is used that has a higher percentage of positive cases with respect to the target cohort, to improve the statistical power.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

See answer above (Target cohort)

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The imaging technique used in the challenge is low-dose computed tomography (CT).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No further context information related to the imaging data is made available.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Context information related to the participant made available:

- Patient sex assigned at birth (male/female)

- Patient age (unit: years)

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Thorax of individuals at high-risk for developing lung cancer, shown in low-dose CT.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Malignancy risk classification of lesions affecting the lungs.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

The goal of the developed AI algorithms is to provide a lesion-level risk score, similar to the approach used in the PanCan model (McWilliams et al., 2013). Therefore, properties of the AI algorithms to be optimized for are lesion-level malignancy risk estimation. A lesion-level risk score corresponds to a score between 0-100 for one lesion (nodule) in a specific CT image. Scores closer to 0 indicate a lower risk of malignancy, while scores closer to 100 indicate a higher malignancy risk.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The datasets consist of low-dose chest CT scans collected as part of a national-wide lung cancer screening programs. These scans were acquired using scanners from GE Healthcare, Siemens, Toshiba, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All CT scans were acquired with a low radiation exposure protocol that is consistent with its lung cancer screening protocols.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

This retrospective study includes low-dose chest CT scans, acquired between 2002-2004, at 33 centers in the United States (Aberle et al., 2011). Additionally, it includes low-dose chest CT scans acquired at one Danish institution (Gentofte University Hospital in Copenhagen) as part of the DLCST study (Pedersen et al., 2009), low-dose chest CT scans acquired as part of the Multicentric Italian Lung Detection (MILD) study (Pastorino et al., 2019), and low-dose chest CT scans acquired at three Dutch institutions (University Medical Center Groningen, University Medical Center Utrecht, and Kennemer Gasthuis Haarlem) and one Belgian Institution (University Hospital Gasthuisberg Leuven) as part of the NELSON study (Ru Zhao et al., 2011).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All imaging acquisitions were performed by trained CT radiographers.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

The training, tuning, and test datasets all consist of low-dose chest CT scans sourced from lung cancer screening trials, including NLST, DLCST, MILD, and NELSON. All cases in these datasets were annotated by experienced radiologists that provided lesion-level binary annotations for the presence/absence of lung cancer. Malignant cases were confirmed through histopathological examination, while benign cases were verified based on their stability over a follow-up period of at least two years.

A case refers to all information that is available for one lesion (nodule) in a specific study. This information always includes image information (full CT scan, and 3D volume around the lesion), and includes context information at patient level. Challenge participants have the flexibility to design their own training strategies for developing their AI algorithms, and are free to use this information in any combination.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

o Public Training and Development Dataset (6163 cases from NLST):

This dataset includes 2120 patients and 4069 CT scans, with 555 annotated malignant nodules and 5608 benign nodules. The data is available to all participants and researchers for AI model training and development during the Open Development Phase. The imaging data is provided under a CC BY 4.0 license, while the training annotations are provided under a non-commercial CC-BY-NC 4.0 license.

The imaging data and annotations will be available and maintained at using a Zenodo record from the start of the challenge.

o Hidden Validation and Tuning Cohort (150 cases)

To facilitate a live public leaderboard for model selection and tuning during the Development Phase, participants can test their AI models on a hidden NLST cohort. These cases are completely independent from the training set, with no overlap.

o Hidden Testing Cohort (483 cases from DLCST, MILD, and NELSON)

This cohort is used as a hidden test set to benchmark AI models, radiologists, and to evaluate all statistical hypotheses at the end of the Closing Testing Phase and the Reader Study.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The Training and Development Dataset (6163 cases) provides researchers and enthusiasts, to the best of our knowledge, with the largest well-annotated publicly available dataset containing low-dose CT for lung nodule risk estimation. A dataset with such numbers allows participants to develop reliable AI algorithms at present-time and through the coming years.

The Hidden Validation and Tuning cohort (150 cases) facilitates a meaningful performance estimate during the Open Development Phase and provides participating teams a way to evaluate their AI model on unseen data.

The Hidden Testing cohort (483 cases) is used to rigorously benchmark the performance of AI models and radiologists at the end of the challenge. The use of external data from different screening trials ensures a diverse, unseen hidden test set for unbiased evaluation that allows for a meaningful analysis of the performance of AI algorithms and human experts.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The distribution of nodule classes in the NLST dataset consists of 13% malignant and 87% benign nodules. All nodules within the NLST cohort are ≥ 4 mm. Malignant nodules have a mean size of 14.42 ± 9.31 mm (median: 11.90 mm), while benign nodules are smaller, averaging 7.38 ± 4.49 mm (median: 5.80 mm). The majority of nodules are solid (430 malignant, 4,860 benign), with part-solid nodules being less common (125 malignant, 748 benign).

The class distribution and nodule information of the hidden testing cohort will remain blinded, to ensure a fair analysis of performance of AI models and radiologists, until the study is officially completed. However, we are disclosing that the hidden test cohort is cancer-enriched, containing a higher proportion of malignant nodules than typically seen in screening populations, though benign nodules still outnumber malignant ones. Additionally, all nodules in this cohort fall within the indeterminate size range (5–15mm), representing the most clinically relevant cases. In this setting, AI algorithms may have the greatest potential to reduce unnecessary procedures and enhance patient outcomes. This focus was determined in consultation with our Scientific Advisory Board

(SAB), where they emphasized the importance of evaluating AI in challenging, potentially high-impact cases.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The lesion annotations of the Training and Development Dataset were previously not publicly available. With our challenge, we therefore release a total of 6163 previously unpublished annotations and corresponding malignancy labels.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For all cases, malignant nodules were confirmed through histopathological examination, while benign nodules were verified based on their stability over a median follow-up period of at least 6 years.

The cases in the training and validation cohort were annotated by an experienced radiologist (>5 years of experience) and two medical students (4th and 5th year of undergraduate studies) after being trained by the experienced radiologist. The experienced radiologist had annotated all the malignant nodules in participants across multiple screening rounds while the nodules of the participants that were not diagnosed with lung cancer were annotated by the two medical students.

The cases in the hidden test cohort were annotated by two thoracic radiologists performing double reading during screening.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotators were given information on the lobar locations and CT section numbers, as the exact nodule coordinates were not available. By retrospectively examining images from participants with lung cancer diagnosis across multiple screening rounds, all nodules exhibiting malignant morphologic features within the tumor-bearing lobe were confidently classified as lung cancer. Nodules not meeting this criterion were excluded from the study. For participants without a lung cancer diagnosis, a similar approach of using the lobe location and CT section number was used during annotation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The nodules in the training and validation dataset were annotated by an experienced radiologists (>5 years of reading lung cancer screening CT) and two medical students which were in their 4th and 5th years of undergraduate studies.

The nodules in the hidden test set were annotated by two experienced thoracic radiologists that also were responsible for the initial readings during the course of screening.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each case was annotated by one annotator, making the need to merge multiple annotations not applicable.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The initial raw training data included low-dose chest CT scans in DICOM-format. We have converted the CT scans from DICOM to MHA format using the panimg Python library: <https://github.com/DIAGNijmegen/rse-panimg>

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

For all cases, malignant nodules were confirmed through histopathological examination, while benign nodules were verified based on their stability over a median follow-up period of at least 6 and 8 years, for the training and hidden test set respectively. This approach ensures objective ground truth labels, effectively removing potential bias in the class labels from the annotation process and increasing the reliability of our dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Not applicable.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The primary performance metric for evaluating and ranking the AI algorithms is the area under the receiver operating characteristics curve (AUC). AUC is chosen as the final ranking score for the challenge, as this metric is the threshold-independent golden standard measure for evaluating the discriminative performance of a classifier.

In LUNA25, each AI algorithm is required to assign a continuous malignancy risk score (ranging from 0 to 1) for each lung nodule in the Hidden Test Cohort. Once all risk scores are calculated, the AUC is computed by comparing these scores against the ground truth labels. The AUC calculation will be performed using the scikit-learn library in Python.

To ensure transparency, the source code for the evaluation will be made publicly available at the start of the challenge. The performance of the AI algorithms will be made publicly available on a public leaderboard, which sequentially is used to determine the best performing AI algorithm.

While AUC is the primary ranking metric, we additionally report specificity at 95% sensitivity and sensitivity at 95% specificity on the public leaderboard to provide further information regarding algorithm performance. However, these additional metrics are not used for ranking the AI algorithms, as comparing models based on such operating points in a clinically relevant context remains challenging.

The equations for sensitivity and specificity are the following:

Sensitivity = True Positives (TP) / (True Positives (TP) + False Negatives (FN))

Specificity = True Negatives (TN) / (True Negatives (TN) + False Positives (FP))

Where:

TP (True Positives): Malignant nodules correctly identified as malignant.

TN (True Negatives): Benign nodules correctly identified as benign.

FN (False Negatives): Malignant nodules incorrectly identified as benign.

FP (False Positives): Benign nodules incorrectly identified as malignant.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

See answer to section above (Metric(s))

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The final ranking of the algorithms will be obtained based on their performance (AUC) on the hidden testing cohort. Here, AUC will be used as a lesion-level metric, where each case (lung nodule) should get an individual score from the AI algorithm. AUC provides a threshold-independent evaluation of AI performance.

Additional metrics such as specificity and sensitivity are included on the public leaderboard but are not used for final ranking. These metrics depend on a fixed operating point, which we believe must be defined based on clinically relevant operating points. With our reader study, we aim to assess multiple clinical operating points that reflect where radiologists currently operate. However, predefining these thresholds in a way that aligns AI and radiologist performance remains challenging. Therefore, we have chosen AUC as the primary performance metric.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions with missing results will be disqualified, and not presented on the leaderboard.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

In clinical practice and in our testing set, a single image may contain multiple lesions, each requiring an individual risk assessment by the radiologist. To reflect this workflow, our evaluation requires AI algorithms to assign an individual malignancy risk score for each lung nodule, ensuring that every lesion is assessed separately. For example, if an image contains multiple nodules, each nodule receives its own independent risk score, rather than

a single score for the entire image.

This allows users to rank an image based on the highest risk lesion present. If an image contains both a high-risk and a low-risk lesion, its ranking is determined by the high-risk lesion which would then decide the clinical follow-up. This approach aligns with the widely known Lung-RADS guidelines that aid radiologists in the interpretation of findings on screening CT.

Given this lesion-level risk assessment, AUC is the most appropriate metric to evaluate AI performance since it provides a threshold-independent measure of how well an AI algorithm can discriminate between malignant and benign lesions.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Statistical tests are performed at the end of the LUNA25 challenge, when the best AI algorithm is selected, and the performance of radiologists is assessed during the reader study. The tests are performed using the best AI algorithm and the average performance of the radiologists on the hidden testing cohort. The source code and details for running these tests will be made available at the start of the challenge.

With the statistical test we address the primary hypothesis of the LUNA25 challenge: the performance of a state-of-the-art AI algorithm with respect to the average performance of a panel of radiologists from the reader study. This statistical analysis (mean AUCs, p-values, and 95% CI) is computed through a multi-reader multi-case (MRMC) analysis (as applied in Saha et al., 2024, McKinney et al., 2020, Rodriguez-Ruiz et al., 2019) using the "IMRMC-R v1.25: Application for Analyzing and Sizing MRMC Reader Studies" package in the R software.

With the MRMC analysis, a non-inferiority test (with a non-inferiority margin of 0.05) is performed to compare performance of the best AI algorithm with the average performance of the radiologists. Non-inferiority is concluded if the AUC difference between AI and readers is greater than 0 and the lower bound of the 95% confidence interval is greater than the non-inferiority margin. If the best AI algorithm is found to be non-inferior to the average radiologists, we proceed with a superiority test with a baseline alpha value of 0.05 to assess if the best AI is also superior to the average radiologists.

A non-inferiority margin of 0.05 will be considered reasonable for the LUNA25 challenge based on the following AUC variations observed in clinicians of a previous reader study in van Riel et al., 2016:

- Thoracic radiologists AUC performance ranged from 0.78 (95%CI: [0.71, 0.85]) to 0.89 (95%CI: [0.84, 0.94])
- Pulmonologists AUC performance ranged from 0.82 (95%CI: [0.75, 0.88]) to 0.83 (95%CI: [0.77, 0.90])
- Radiology residents performance ranged from 0.76 (95%CI: [0.69, 0.83]) to 0.85 (95%CI: [0.79, 0.91])

For the malignancy risk thresholds corresponding to 95% specificity and 95% sensitivity, the observed sensitivity, and specificity were calculated, respectively. These two thresholds were used to evaluate diagnostic performance at clinically relevant decision points, allowing for a comparison of AI algorithm performance when prioritizing sensitivity versus specificity.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

See answer for details on statistical methods.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Reader study: Tasks and interface

Parallel to the AI study, LUNA25 will also conduct a reader study with the objective of evaluating the performance of radiologists with various levels of experience at lung nodule malignancy risk estimation. The reader study will also be conducted using low-dose chest CT examinations, clinical information of the patient (age, gender), and volume and equivalent diameter of the nodule.

Readers will be given a bounding box around the center of the lung nodule for which they have to provide a malignancy risk score between 0 and 100 (with incremental steps of 1). A risk score of 0 indicates very low risk of malignancy and a risk score of 100 indicates a very high risk of malignancy. Such a score allows us to compare radiologists' performance against AI algorithms across a range of operating points. Additionally, readers will provide a management recommendation, categorizing nodules into three risk classes: low, intermediate, or high risk. These classes correspond to: low risk (return to regular screening), intermediate risk (short-term follow-up), and high risk (immediate follow-up, such as referral to a pulmonologist or PET/CT scan). Once readers finalize a case, their answers are saved and can no longer be modified.

Reader study: Study Design

The LUNA25 reader study is hosted on grand-challenge.org/reader-studies/, which supports chest CT viewers and classification tools. The reader study used a subset of 300 cases from the hidden testing cohort. Primary costs of the study are reader time and effort. Reviewing more than 300 cases would require excessive reader effort; however, this approach enables a fully-crossed design while keeping the workload for each reader manageable. Prior to the start of this study, readers are provided a detailed guide on the annotation workflow, including all tools made available on the platform (e.g. navigation, zooming, windowing, measuring scale). They are also provided with access to a practice session to get familiar with the reading interface and the expected workflow. Afterwards, each reader uses their grand-challenge.org account to access their instance of the reader study.

Reader study: Registered radiologists

We include any clinician who reads and reports chest CT examinations in clinical practice. Readers across all

experience levels have been invited to participate in the reader study. The readers will also be asked for their years of experience in reading and reporting chest CT. The names of all readers will be pseudonymized to ensure that individual performance cannot be tracked back to their respective identity. If necessary, only the primary researchers of the LUNA25 challenge will have access to this information.

Scientific Advisory Board:

Conducting high-quality and impactful research requires a well-considered study protocol. This promotes a more reliable evaluation of the results, enabling the scientific community to draw robust conclusions and shape future research directions. To support the quality of findings from the LUNA25 challenge, critical aspects of the study design will be discussed with the Scientific Advisory Board of LUNA25, which comprises of international experts across radiology, pulmonology, epidemiology, AI and a patient representative:

Radiology

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Patient Representative

Lidia Barberio, Director Longkanker Nederland (The Netherlands)

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

This will be made publicly available at the start of the challenge.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

not applicable.